

A Framework for Research Software Engineers Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS	2
THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB	3
OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS	3
THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP	4
CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP	4
NEXT STEPS	10
APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises responses from the workshop held on 14 March 2025 to co-design an upcoming ARDC infrastructure project that aims to provide updated architectural principles, a technology roadmap, and detailed explanations of common Research Software Engineering and research data management patterns for the HASS & Indigenous research community.

This project is part of the Community Data Lab, which fosters the development of tools, datasets and documentation that enable researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, museums, archives and other collections.

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. Since early 2024 we have been undergoing a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure. Co-designing infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders helps the ARDC to create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning new investment in digital research infrastructure for HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research data communities, as part of the [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

The HASS and Indigenous RDC began with the identification of opportunities to accelerate the impact of HASS and Indigenous research in the [2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#). The Australian Government Department of Education commissioned scoping studies to identify investment-ready programs, several of which formed the foundational activities of the HASS and Indigenous RDC.

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish

long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

The ARDC is currently delivering infrastructure in six focus areas, some of which builds upon foundational activities delivered during the first phase of the HASS and Indigenous RDC and some of which are new activities designed in collaboration with the research community. These are:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities
- The Language Data Commons of Australia
- Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
- Australian Internet Observatory
- Australian Creative Histories and Futures
- Connections

THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB

The Community Data Lab is an ongoing activity under the Connections focus area of the HASS and Indigenous RDC. Through the Community Data Lab the ARDC seeks to improve researchers' ability to utilise the data made available from galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) and other collections. This activity provides tools, datasets and guidance that meet needs shared by researchers with different research problems from multiple disciplines. The outputs of the first phase of the Community Data Lab are now available for use by researchers.

During the delivery of this phase, the ARDC developed a set of principles for the design of sustainable HASS infrastructure, which are (in brief):

- A preference for “infrastructure at rest” over infrastructure which requires costly active support
- The separation of data from analytics
- Efficiency and flexibility of platform design
- Reusable code
- Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents

The ARDC is now in the process of developing Phase 2 of the Community Data Lab to expand this suite of data, tools and guidance materials.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the

people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

We began Problem Identification in 2024, by calling openly for registrations of interest from partners who might be able to help us to design and deliver projects for the Community Data Lab. We targeted groups at universities that provide research software engineering and data analytics support to HASS researchers, because these groups have strong experience building solutions for researchers and exposure to a range of current researcher needs. We brought potential partners together for a series of roundtable discussions. Through these discussions we identified a set of possible projects which would each serve the needs of researchers from multiple disciplines across multiple research institutions, and which could be developed in line with the principles described above.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the open co-design workshop described below. The workshop was advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP

The proposed project aims to provide updated architectural principles, a technology roadmap, and detailed explanations of common Research Software Engineering and research data management patterns for the HASS & Indigenous research community. This project is being developed in partnership with The Australian National University HASS Digital Research Hub.

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

The co-design workshop was held virtually on 14th March 2025. The workshop was open to all and was attended by 28 participants from 16 organisations. Organisations represented included 11 Australian universities, as well as government organisations, research infrastructure providers and consulting companies.

The workshop aimed to refine our understanding of the challenge, validate the problem statement and its impact, confirm the user base for the proposed solution, and gather feedback on the proposed solution’s features. Dr Peter Sefton (University of Queensland) presented on the challenge, which was summarised with the following problem statement:

“The humanities, arts, social sciences (HASS) and Indigenous research community faces a shortage of research software engineering (RSE) expertise, leading to fragmented and inconsistent software development practices. Researchers and technical teams lack access to architectural guidance, technical roadmaps, a recommended patterns guide for RSE, and models to integrate RSE principles into their work. This produces inefficiencies in technical delivery, increases cybersecurity risk, and makes it difficult to sustain research software beyond individual projects. Without a coordinated effort to build RSE capability across the sector, the HASS and Indigenous research community will struggle to leverage computational methods and produce innovative, reproducible, secure, and sustainable digital outputs.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

Have we described the problem correctly?

- RSE career pathways and support
 - Lack of career pathways for RSEs
 - Start to build HASS&I RSE as a career path with specific skills
- Understanding the RSE’s role and value
 - A research software engineer is not the same as research software engineering practices. Distinction between approaches and people is important
 - Lack of recognition of the value and importance of RSEs
 - One of the issues not addressed in the statement is the lack of understanding of the value that RSEs can bring to the domain
- Lack of infrastructure and funding
 - The problem is not so much lack of guidance but the lack of funding for ongoing maintenance and support
 - The problem statement is correct but to solve this also needs to address the funding models for research and how software fits into this
- Distinction between RSEs, software engineers and researchers
 - We can’t expect all HASS researchers to be proficient in software engineering
 - Differentiate between research software development vs commercial software development
- Uniqueness of the HASS sector

- HASS software development has some unique challenges around the client knowledge and experience in RSE that impacts communication
- Connecting to how this issue is solved in other fields like biology etc. would be good. HASS isn't as we often think it is
- HASS very broad - we don't always know the commonalities and the difference between different disciplines - issues of language used across disciplines
- Communication and collaboration
 - The problem statement is overly focused on RSEs - should this work be about the research development ecosystem/building community - the research software development ecosystem needs: RSEs, data scientists, data librarians/data specialists.
 - The problem statement It's good, but there could perhaps be more emphasis on communication and community development. New frameworks would be great, but how do we collaborate around them?
 - Making sure people know the work that is happening
- Sustainability and maintenance issues
 - Technical teams who end up with the maintenance burden of DH platforms
 - It's a good thing for (some) software to no longer be built - maintenance is a cost

Who is this problem important to?

- Research Software Engineers
- HASS Researchers
- Funding bodies
- Developers and technical contributors
- Digital Research Infrastructure organisations
- Community and collaboration stakeholders

Other considerations raised were around standards, frameworks and best practices

- HASS researchers often perceive themselves to have less tech skills, so a set of standards and guides would help people being tasked with bridging between research and tech
- Challenge the orthodoxy that promotes Jupyter Notebooks as the preferred interface. Very small proportion of HASS researchers are comfortable engaging with APIs

Would addressing this problem be valuable (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)

- Infrastructure sustainability and reusable tools
 - Sustainable open infrastructure and tools that can enhance HASS research and support researchers
 - It would be useful to extend any learning, tools, techniques to other domains
 - Not just design patterns but reusable tools and libraries
- Clear guidance, education and support for researchers

- Useful for software engineers who are new to working in the HASS software development
- Researchers can concentrate less on data access and more on actual research
- A reference point for researchers to educate their IT departments about recommended patterns in HASS RSE
- Community building and support
 - Building and maintaining communities to support, develop and maintain sustainable HASS infrastructure is not a trivial undertaking and takes many different stakeholders and skill sets
 - Enable collaboration outsider of the software ecosystem
 - Finding solutions, such as development and advertising a RSE HASS Community of practice could help.
- Interoperability and efficiency
 - Interoperability both within the domain and cross-domain can be enhanced
 - Data could be consumed more widely and used in novel ways for better research
- Other considerations
 - International modelling
 - Environmental benefits: patterns for deciding between closed and open, massive and minimal infrastructure
 - How will these guidelines and so forth (the solution) reach the intended audience? Is this project proposing some sort of unified outreach? Who is the audience? Is it RSEs in the HASS space specifically?

Activity 2: Where do you go to find out if someone has solved a software problem already in HASS and Indigenous research? Where do you share your own solutions?

- Research software sharing platforms and practices
 - Github
 - Code repositories on Zenodo
 - Google
 - The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN)
 - Software Sustainability Institute
 - Subreddits can be good sources of communities working on shared interests
- Generative AI
 - Younger software engineers are going to AI first
 - GenAI is a big part of development workflows now
- Academic outputs
 - Paper output is the best way to share your work
 - There are good digital humanities journals
- Community and collaboration
 - Slack channels

- Disciplinary organisations and conferences
- Ask fellow team members who've worked on similar projects
- Talk to people
- Challenges in sharing solutions
 - If tools were made with reuse in mind rather than reuse being an afterthought, then we may be able to reuse them more
 - Existing approaches are often useful for reference but integration can be more trouble than it's worth
- Other comments
 - I really don't want to see yet another directory/catalogue
 - A Research Software Encyclopedia could be a potential, lightweight solution for a HASS research software catalogue. This has been developed by people from the Society of RSE and USE-RSE orgs: <https://rseng.github.io/rse/>
 - Have researcher-first SE's been exposed to problems from other disciplines and projects?

Activity 3: Do you have examples of common problems and solutions that you encounter regularly when building HASS and Indigenous research software?

- Sustainability and maintenance issues
 - Software requires constant maintenance.
 - Collections are held hostage by obsolete platforms
 - Ongoing sustainability because things are built by individuals who move on
 - Lack of funding to support maintenance of the software developed after the research project has finished
- Lack of clear specifications and problem definition
 - There are often misunderstandings between software developers and researchers (the latter don't get what they want because they can't articulate what they want)
 - Biggest recurring problem is underspecified problems or goals
- Interoperability and domain-specific requirements
 - Interoperable systems are crucial and cohesion is essential but difficult
 - Collaborating across universities on software is difficult
 - Legacy software and projects that people want to hold on to but aren't interoperable with new projects or can't be built on
- Institutional barriers and infrastructure limitations
 - University supported HASS focused platforms like Omeka behind the university VPN - so can't have external collaborators
 - Inconsistent access and licensing of data in the GLAM sector

- Systems like Github are heavily used but often go against ITS security policies
- Barrier to entry for non coders needing to look after infrastructure concerns
- Software design and development
 - Text analytics software often treats either the word or the document as the basic unit and software is built on that premise- for humanities researchers that is quite limiting as there are important units between
 - Lack of GPU resources for model training and resource for analysis and storage for large HASS datasets
 - Develop policies for open sourcing of software developments
 - The HASS space is a wide space - it's difficult to build a monolithic system
 - Whiteboarding ideas, jupyter notebooks, dashboards, Zenodo
 - If a prototype is abandoned - clear agreements with what happens with the data
- Researcher engagement and capability building
 - Articulate a vision for how HASS research infrastructure can scale (not just in terms of compute but in terms of implementation consulting) to serve the numbers of HASS researchers and HDR students
 - As well as developing solutions you need to communicate with researchers the value of these solutions and support the development of necessary skills
 - Design a policy framework for partnering with private sector organisations

Activity 4: What new or current but unused technology would you like to explore in HASS and Indigenous research? Be as specific as possible (i.e. not “AI” but “using LLM’s for sentiment analysis on public interest documents”)

- Artificial Intelligence
 - Image AI for automated image annotation
 - AI for exploring datasets
 - LLM for translation
 - Vibe coding
 - AI to generate data visualisations from text/tables
- Data Spaces
 - This helps implement FAIR and CARE principles
 - Graph databases
- Open-source and cloud technologies
 - Openstack
 - Cloud tech in general but alternatives to commercial cloud
 - Function as a Service (FaaS)
- Access control for sensitive information
 - Trusted Research Environments

- Considerations around integrating existing and new technologies
 - Focus on the new always marginalises well established but useful tools and approaches
 - Combining old things in new ways
- Simplified research processes and tools
 - Easy to use pipeline to get large dataset from raw format to data analysis, visualisation and machine learning
 - Organisational information management systems, bringing everything together and building it in a modular way.
- Other considerations
 - Computing within constraints (what if the output must be a static website?, what if it needs to run only a low spec laptop from 5 years ago?)
 - Sector search, semantic search

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close end of day Friday 23 May. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2025.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line 'RSE Framework'.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES

Full text of workshop responses

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Have we described the problem correctly?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● need a co-designed solution to create a structured way to provide information to research community ● HASS software development has some unique challenges around the client knowledge and experience in RSE that impacts communication ● (HASS software development has some unique challenges around the client knowledge and experience in RSE that impacts communication) Don't agree e.g. Requirements engineering is an SE knowledge area with techniques, to translate client knowledge into software solutions, that can be applied across domains. HASS is not special. ● problem not so much lack of guidance but lack of funding for ongoing maintenance / support +2 ● Is this for Software Engineers working on HASS & I RDC projects. Does that allow space for people who are just Software Engineers to join in if they do not have a research background ● Distinguish RSE as career path from the software engineering challenges in the HASS & I domain ● Lack of stable career pathways for RSEs ● The RSE domain is characterised by a high degree of novice practitioners. Architectural and Design Patterns are the key technique for transferral of knowledge from experts to novices. ● Research Software Engineers without a SE background need different remedial work if they are researchers turned RSE ● It's good, but there could perhaps be more emphasis on communication and community development. New frameworks would be great, but how do we collaborate around them? ● There is also a lack of engagement due to existing culture not traditionally utilising RSEs or software driven solutions for research in the domain. ● One of the issues not addressed in the statement is the lack of understanding of the value that RSEs can bring to the domain. ● Are there standard or established RSE principles? ● (Are there standard or established RSE principles?) yes. they are called 'software engineering principles' see SWEBOK. ● It is difficult to summarise in just a few sentences, but this describes the overall problem for RSEs (I keep noting what it takes to build and maintain sustainable infrastructure, and it includes entire communities, not just RSEs). Key points for RSEs are not restricted only to this sector, but may be more of an issue...a lack of career pathways, funding of infrastructure maintenance (not just development of the new thing), recognition of the value and importance of RSEs. Are we able to leverage off (any?) existing frameworks, adjusting to specific HASS needs? ● The problem statement is correct but to solve this also needs to

	<p>address the funding models for research and how software fits into this. And the funding for different scale projects from small research groups, to LIEF to NRI.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Connecting to how this issue is solved in other fields like biology etc. would be good. HASS isn't as we often think it is ● I understand the lack of RSEs in HASS but how does this solve the issue? ● (I understand the lack of RSEs in HASS but how does this solve the issue?) It begins the process of creating a baseline that people who aren't RSEs can work to, and a set of professional standards and principles that can make RSE careers more attractive. ● We can't expect all HASS researchers to be proficient in software engineering. maybe there needs to be a bridging person or channel ● lack access to career supports ● differentiate research software development vs commercial software development ● Research software engineer != research software engineering practices. Distinction between approaches and people is important ● starts to build HASS&I RSE as a career path (with specific skills) ● also lacking access to infrastructure resources ● differentiate between researchers who can code vs professional software developers /engineers who have actually worked in teams to develop systems that can be maintained and sustained ● making sure people know the work is happening ● Requirements gathering, project planning, and execution ● This is framed solely as a deficit and a lack - I think this devalues what is already there, and the research work that is already happening ● Need a mix of researchers and professional software developers ● HASS very broad - we don't always know the commonalities and the difference between different disciplines; issues of language across disciplines - commonalities and differences ● It's a good thing for (some) software to no longer be built - maintenance is a cost +2 ● Challenge the RSE orthodoxy. Other domains use a consulting model. ● (Challenge the RSE orthodoxy. Other domains use a consulting model.) I was under the impression RSE orthodoxy (if it exists at all) is <u>_grounded_</u> in consulting and collaboration. If it isn't in some organizations this would be a good opportunity to push back, certainly! ● Consider developing researchers with PM skill sets to become consultants rather the emphasis on developing researchers into professional software developers. ● Existing tooling and standards need to be adopted wherever possible. Researchers need to be prepared to look outside their domains ● HASS - everything that is not STEM, so not always strong commonalities ● The problem statement is overly focused on RSEs - should this work be about the research development ecosystem/building community - the research software development ecosystem needs: RSEs, data
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	<p>scientists, data librarians/data specialists...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (The problem statement is overly focused on RSEs - should this work be about the research development ecosystem/building community - the research software development ecosystem needs: RSEs, data scientists, data librarians/data specialists....) There is a Research Technology Professionals (RTP) acronym, which most RSEs are happy to contribute to, which covers all those areas. The question is whether that would dilute the purpose of the proposed work too much. RTP discussions tend to be at the level of career development and advocacy for technical careers because of the broad range of technical practices. ● Technical teams who end up with the maintenance burden of DH platforms ● This is tied to a job role, but would a set of guides for good SE work help researchers who specify and monitor output to know what a good SE would do... so a checklist? ● Part of work package could be an environmental scan to identify who is researcher who started working on SE, and who has SE background. So different people with different needs identified ● In general, but it's fairly specific to the individual (RSE), where as much of what we're talking about is related to researcher-professional collaborations (from survey)
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Who is the problem important to?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● This is important for a large range of stakeholders. This covers not only RSEs but also HASS researchers, funding bodies, contributors/owners of data. ● Researchers who want to design and build innovative bespoke outputs but maximise their sustainability. ● HASS researchers often perceive themselves to have less tech skills, so a set of standards and guides would help people being tasked with bridging between research and tech ● HASS researchers who need clear but flexible frameworks to design and sustain their projects. ● Technical postdocs, who need frameworks and patterns to work to, and the academic colleagues they work with who need quality sustainable projects. ● Is the RR focus needed here.. just SEs? ● (Is the RR focus needed here.. just SEs?) Software Engineering in a research context can be quite different ● Funders, who need high quality and sustainable results from investment. +1 ● digital research infrastructure organisations within universities ● Developers in a range of contexts, not just those employed in RSE positions. IE contributors to open source projects, researchers who tinker with some code to meet a specific need ● no reason why research software should be developed by non professional developers.

- (no reason why research software should be developed by non professional developers.) Professional software developers bring code dev & maintenance expertise that researchers generally do not possess. Teams should be prof devops
- HASS researchers who get their data and research workflows trapped in proprietary, unsustainable websites and web apps +6
- "(HASS researchers who get their data and research workflows trapped in proprietary, unsustainable websites and web apps +6) I totally agree with this. I have evangelised widely to researchers about the merit of solutions like Obsidian, which give researchers ownership and control of their data
- however, the learning curve is often viewed as too steep
- i think the adoption issue is partly about being able to communicate how software can be embedded at all stages in the research lifecycle +1"
- Challenge the orthodoxy that HASS researchers can accept Jupyter Notebooks. Very small proportion are comfortable engaging with APIs
- (Challenge the orthodoxy that HASS researchers can accept Jupyter Notebooks. Very small proportion are comfortable engaging with APIs) The GLAM Workbench contains 100+ Jupyter notebooks, working with a variety of APIs that are used by HASS researchers. Jupyter notebooks can be delivered in a variety of ways, as web apps, dashboards, or traditional notebooks depending on user needs, but of course there also needs to be skills development and scaffolding +1
- Develop RSE by starting with professional developer and developing their domain knowledge
- Revisit the analysis that supports an architecture that promotes Jupyter notebooks as the preferred UX. Overwhelming majority of HASS researcher can't and don't want to engage with API's
- (Revisit the analysis that supports an architecture that promotes Jupyter notebooks as the preferred UX. Overwhelming majority of HASS researcher can't and don't want to engage with API's) there's a related question here about whether it is appropriate to be looking at upskilling researchers. The Biologists did a lot of sector wide work on this a decade ago for example and did a big investment in skills development (not saying notebooks are the only game in town)
- Colleagues (technical or non-technical) who need an 'authority' or reference point they can point to.
- People using AI coding tools to build their own software (vibe coding), but uncertain about how to align it to RSE and RDM requirements.
- Develop standards for usage of contemporary UI development frameworks
- From a university perspective - those who build the infrastructure (project teams, RSEs, researchers etc), funders, external stakeholders (looking for sustainable open infrastructure over commercial options), advisory groups, research and contracts office and internal funders (is supporting the infrastructure a priority for the institution, if so, how can processes be improved so stakeholders who can and

	<p>wish to support open infrastructures developed by RSEs are able to? How can communities use, support and maintain these infrastructures be developed? It takes many skills and many different stakeholders, from RSEs and researchers, to business development and marketing, advisory and governance, community engagement etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop standards for a workflow framework (adopt rather than develop) that can be deployed across DH projects ● how to improve processes and quality using existing strategies such as Lean, DevOps and Agile ● The RSE field is under resourced. Efficiency gains allow research to be more productive but allowing RSE'ing to be going on. Also, poor practices discourage continued participation in the RSE workforce, which compounds the shortage of good RSEs. (from survey)
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Would addressing this problem be valuable? (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clarity about the technical direction ARDC want to take, so researchers can align their projects to it. ● What would be enabled- hopefully in the end, sustainable open infrastructures and tools that can enhance HASS research and support researchers. Building and maintaining communities to support, develop and maintain sustainable HASS infrastructure is not a trivial undertaking and takes many different stakeholders and skillsets. ● Addressing the issues identified in the problem statement would definitely be valuable. It would also be useful to extend any learnings, tools, techniques, etc. to other domains. ● By solving the identified issues, interoperability both within the domain and cross-domain can be enhanced. This accelerates development and benefit realisation. ● International modelling ● How will these guidelines and so forth (the solution) reach the intended audience? Is this project proposing some sort of unified outreach? Who is the audience? Is it RSEs in the HASS space specifically? ● Guide to testing would be useful - all steps of process broken down ● Researchers will be at different stages in a maturity cycle. Often early career researchers, have to work with mid- and late-career researchers, who may be less willing to change research (mgmt) practices any innovations must be able to enable collaboration outside of the software ecosystem ● Software Engineer who are new to working in the HASS software development ● Environmental benefits: patterns for deciding between closed and open, massive and minimal infrastructure. ● Finding solutions, such as development and advertising a RSE HASS Community of practice could help. ● Interoperability and hopefully efficiency.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear guidance for Software Engineers to become Research Software Engineers +1 ● Helping people navigate issues related to closed and open infrastructure platforms and systems (AWS vs OpenStack) ● Data could be consumed more widely and used in novel ways for better research ● Hopefully a self-sustaining community that supports the development of HASS research software ● Researchers can concentrate less on data access and more on actual research ● A reference point for researchers to educate their IT departments about recommended patterns in HASS RSE. ● Not just design patterns but reusable tools and libraries ● Clearly yes, but 'solving' this problem is unlikely. There is also a kind of deficit framing here which is a bit unhelpful in understanding how interdisciplinary teams get things done by leaning on the strengths. (from survey)
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Activity 2

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Where do you go to find out if someone has solved a software problem already in HASS and Indigenous research? Where do you share your own solutions?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revisit the preference for Jupyter notebooks in the context of ubiquitous proliferation of generative AI ● I use github, searching for repositories with projects related to my needs/purposes ● Not invented here may stop people from going to communities/tools that could help them. Is this a HASS/I software or just software problem? +1 ● 1. You need to know the research background anyway. Software solutions are mentioned in the literature. Occasionally some individual has collected relevant work in an area on a Github. This seems like good practice. 2. Same. Paper output is the best way to share your work. ● Have researcher-first SE's been exposed to problems from other disciplines and projects ● Some solutions are in corporate world ● there are good digital humanities journals - but no time to read them! ● Sharing solutions is hard, but there's always adding links to code and data in publications ● Subreddits can be good sources of communities working on shared interests ● There are a number of existing models for research software directories ● (There are a number of existing models for research software directories) Examples of ones that are actually sustainable and working? ● I really don't want to see yet another directory/catalogue +3

- (I really don't want to see yet another directory/catalogue +3) This would not be a sustainable activity for CDL
- Code and workflows are shared on GitHub via an Organisation and code repositories, usually archived on Zenodo (dois for research software, looking into what PIDs may be used). For software solutions that already exist, we work extensively with collaborators in the space to be aware of similar initiatives/solutions (particularly open science or access programs funded by the European Commission). Communicating the solution/work is vital- via publications, conferences, working groups, linkedin, community engagements to raise awareness of what we have built and understanding what already exists. Working together to not rebuild the wheel (again) is always the aim, but repetition still occurs due to funding cycles and individual research projects, and it comes back to the development of community led initiatives and priorities- who lead this? Tracking use and impact of software still has not been solved!
- A Research Software Encyclopedia could be a potential, lightweight solution for a HASS research software catalogue. This has been developed by people from the Society of RSE and USE-RSE orgs: <https://rseng.github.io/rse/>, <https://rseng.github.io/rse/>, <https://rseng.github.io/rse/>
- To find I search Github/Pypi (et al), and also bookmark a lot of stuff that gets shared on social media. I also look at what other projects are using.
- Sharing code and tools through Github, Pypi, Zenodo (minting DOIs), and my own websites. +1
- Finding effective ways of sharing solutions with researchers who might benefit is HARD. I share through social media, email lists, Slack channels, give presentations, share through disciplinary organisations and conferences. It's a lot of work on top of the actual coding.
- github repositories of libraries: <https://github.com/jellydn/awesome-typesafe>, <https://github.com/jellydn/awesome-typesafe>
- if tools were made with reuse in mind rather than reuse being an afterthought, then we may be able to reuse more +1
- ask for suggestions on online communities or forums such as rse-aunz <http://rse-aunz.org/>, <http://rse-aunz.org/>, <http://rse-aunz.org/>
- Google, Github, Paperwithcode
- Ask fellow team members who've worked on similar projects recently
- professional developers review frameworks independent of domain
- Problem definitions are more important than solutions - superficially similar solutions may obscure important details
- Revisit the market fit methodology currently being used. Is analysis of ARC project requirements being undertaken.
- CRAN
- Software sustainability institute
- I've started adding RO-Crate metadata files to code repositories to enhance findability and to explicitly link code to documentation, examples, and datasets.+1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Existing approaches are often useful for reference but integration can be more trouble than it's worth. ● The highest compliment is if my ideas are reimplemented without imposing maintenance constraints on my own code. ● GenAI is a big part of dev workflows now ● issues with maintenance, oftentimes it's more exciting to develop a shiny new thing ● I talk to people... a lot of people ● Younger software engineers are not seeking out design packages socially, but go to AI first solo ● Other NRI or tech groups ● people seem to go to technology specific communities rather than discipline specific +1 ● RSE mailing list for AU/NZ ● International : SSI UK, eResearch Netherlands, Alan Turing ● Question is badly worded. The software problem may have already been solved but not in the HASS&I domain ● Develop standards for a workflow framework (adopt rather than develop) that can be deployed across DH projects ● PyPi, StackOverflow, LLMs (!) +1 ● "My area is narrow enough that I know most of what is going on because I read the academic literature, and it's good practice for RSE outputs to be reported in literature even if it's not our KPI, so's to speak. This assumes we're talking about a highly specific problem, but mostly solving any problem is a collection of generic data/technical solutions. The usual sources of knowledge in that respect hold true. ● I have also observed that the era of AI coding is making developers more prone to accepting default solutions and not looking more broadly. This is a danger zone for us. FWIW, I very much enjoyed the human interaction with other RSEs in this workshop. I think we should do more of it, and I'm going to give it a go in the AIO where we have a number of engineers across the work packages. (from survey)"
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Activity 3

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Do you have examples of common problems and solutions that you encounter regularly when building HASS and Indigenous research software?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Academia's promotion criteria does not favour ongoing maintenance of code once problem x is solved ● Operationalising to solve just research problem x, not thinking about longevity ● whiteboarding ideas, jupyter notebooks, dashboards, Zenodo ● Versioning of software to record changes, derivatives and version ● Software requires constant maintenance. This aspect can be easily overlooked, ● Decoupling software and data enables reuse

- If problem = fail, researchers may still learn a lot that leads to great future research
- Develop policies for open sourcing of software developments. +1
- Mistaking efficiency for effectiveness
- Repurposing tools that aren't quite right, because that's still better than developing something new.
- Not a 'problem, but incorporating Indigenous communities, particularly when relevant for data sovereignty
- Stakeholders at different stages of maturity, meaning that needs vary across the different stakeholder groups +1
- The HASS space is a wide space - it's difficult to build a monolithic system
- Software for specific projects vs generic software (which can be reused)
- Issues could be with software engineers who are new to the research space but might be drawing from their previous experience which might not be suitable for the research environment
- Interoperable for who and for what purpose/along what dimensions?
- Interoperable systems are therefore crucial, cohesion essential but difficult
- Software from one discipline is superficially applicable to other domains - but misses key things for the new domain which make it not very useful
- no 2 engagements are the same - varying levels of stakeholder engagements of what can be achieved and at what cost, a potentially convoluted discussion
- Defining the problem *in the research domain* then it's translation into a software design (or selection from existing tools/methods/workflows) +1
- Design a policy framework for partnering with private sector organizations.
- Software infrastructure vs rock-solid standardised components being available (e.g. good, stable libraries)
- Text analytics software often treats either the word or the document as the basic unit and software is built on that premise- for humanities researchers that is quite limiting as there are important units between +2
- Software dev often focuses on features at the expense of long term access to well described data - and solutions become unsustainable +1
- Lack of specification and identification of pain points
- Academics developing software in HASS often don't get recognition / reward within universities.+1
- Stakeholder engagement and cross disciplinary teams are crucial, and it can be hard to get right. We have RSE's who are experienced in software development who have been introduced to HASS, technical staff engaging with HASS researchers and specialists to apply professional software development to build HASS tools. The ability to talk and translate across domains is critical. Sustainability and maintenance of what has been built is our biggest challenge. Is

	<p>it suiting the needs of the communities it was designed for, and is there a community/market for it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When value is measured in number of users, not the quality and utility of the software ● And whether it addresses an actual research problem... ● Software engineers can bring a specific set of skills, but are expected to take on other roles involving domain expertise ● Making a prototype can be a very useful approach ● university supported HASS focused platforms like Omeka behind the university VPN - so can't have external collaborators ● There are often misunderstandings between software developers and researchers (the latter don't get what they want because they can't articulate what they want) +2 ● Premature standardisation along superficial similarities ● Develop reflective practices that help users understand how software design and assumptions can shape the sorts of questions they can ask. Particularly important with AI applications. ● Problem that Uni ITS systems are risk averse to collaboration across universities. Authentication and SSO can be a problem ● Collections are held hostage by obsolete platforms ● Still concern about open source software from ITS and how to manage security ● Lack of GPU resources for model training and resource for analysis and storage for large HASS datasets ● Inconsistent access and licensing of data in the GLAM sector ● Biggest recurring problem: Underspecified problems or goals. Solution: Prototyping as a vital step for problem/potential discovery Example: Prototype built for the CDL a year ago (https://hansardplus.digitalobservatory.net.au/), https://hansardplus.digitalobservatory.net.au/, ● legacy software and projects that people want to hold on to but aren't interoperable with new projects or can't be built on. ● Systems like Github are heavily used but often go against ITS security policies ● Costs of experimenting with AWS etc ● Thinking that an API is the only thing needed for data access ● clear and repeatable ways of specifying the requirements of projects or researchers so that we can build what they want ● lack of funding to support maintenance of the software developed after the research project finished ● Make the stages prototype/ exploration stage to building a tool to address an information management need long term very clear. If a prototype is abandoned - clear agreements with what happens with the data - which can be substantial terabytes ultimately owned by another party / indigenous party which has not thought through what to do with the data in the absence of a functional information management system. Manage end user expectations ● ongoing sustainability because things are built by individuals who move on... +1 ● (ongoing sustainability because things are built by individuals who
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	<p>move on... +1) 100%</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● As well as developing solutions you need to communicate with researchers the value of these solutions and support the development of necessary skills. ● Researchers often underestimate the resource and time needed to develop and maintain the solution; potential solutions is for RSE to document the requirements, priority and time needed, and track changes. ● collaborating across universities on software is difficult - shared resources and systems (like JIRA) +1 ● collaborating across universities because of security/firewall ● Poorly documented / supported APIs in the GLAM sector. ● where to use new tech like serverless or containers or vm's ? ● Design a policy framework to encourage development and consulting companies to invest in HASS research software. ● Articulate a vision for how HASS research infrastructure can scale (not just in terms of compute but in terms of implementation consulting) to serve the numbers of HASS researchers and HDR students. +2 ● barrier to entry for non coders needing to look after infrastructure concerns ● Different timelines & ● The most common problem for software engineering is that the problems are under specified. You can't write a 'spec' if you don't know what the problems and opportunities are yet. The solution for this is to adopt an exploration phase with prototyping. This helps you understand the problem better. There's scarcely nothing I develop these days that doesn't begin as a prototype or a series of them. (from survey)
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Activity 4

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What new or current but unused technology would you like to explore in HASS and Indigenous research? Be as specific as possible (i.e. not “AI” but “using LLM’s for sentiment analysis on public interest documents”)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revisit the preference for Jupyter notebooks in the context of ubiquitous proliferation of generative AI ● Image AI for automated image annotation ● AI for exploring datasets. This was specifically discussed at an ARDC workshop on data donation (AIO). AI thematic analysis, generation of first-pass visualisations etc. More broadly, a pivot to natural language interfaces rather than arcane search UIs and syntax. A lot of this is underway in existing ARDC HASS projects :) ● LLM for translation ● Not enough RSEs for university projects - how can we use AI to help do easy drafting etc. ● Using AI to generate data visualisations from text/tables ● Using AI to generate documentation on projects - some standards

	<p>and best practices for documentation of Research Software</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Some more legacy things like embeddings/vectors for data searching. It's related to AI but it has a great value in semantic discovery. Also, models to extract named entities, and do other NLP tasks. Continue to be useful! ● (Some more legacy things like embeddings/vectors for data searching. It's related to AI but it has a great value in semantic discovery. Also, models to extract named entities, and do other NLP tasks. Continue to be useful!) are these not already being developed within the python environment? what further value-add can the ARDC offer? ● open source alternatives for cloud computing databases/storage ● Data Spaces +1 ● Data Spaces helps implement FAIR and CARE ● workbenches for researchers to mediate usage of AI ● What's a data space? ● (What's a data space?) https://ardc.edu.au/resource/australian-dataspaces-an-introduction-and-faqs/ ● openstack ● (openstack) Openstack is being used very widely already - it's the basis for NeCTAR ● A private workspace for the project with restricted access to sensitive data. +1 ● "(A private workspace for the project with restricted access to sensitive data. +1) There are a number of Trusted Research Environments already available to do this. ● Any examples? ● SURE (Sax Institute), ERICA (UNSW), SeRP (Swansea University), KeyPoint (QCIF)" ● Organisational information management systems (e.g. for ranger programs, protected areas) to solve practical challenges for groups needing to develop work plans, manage multiple sources of information (including culturally sensitive information needing specific individualised access permissions), monitoring programs and analysis with visualisation to close the management loop. Basically bringing everything together and building this in a modular way which can be scaled up as a group grows in capacity and takes on more complex projects such as nature positive/repair markets. ● easy to use pipeline to get large dataset from raw format to data analysis, visualisation and machine learning +1 ● "(easy to use pipeline to get large dataset from raw format to data analysis, visualisation and machine learning +1) Who would benefit from this pipeline? researchers or research administrators and data custodians? ● currently, some datasets that i work with are massive multiple-sheet excel spreadsheets and I know that it deters researchers from using the data ● researchers with any research data, formats are not limited. +1" ● Minimalist computing: computing within constraints (what if the
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	<p>output must be a static website?, what if it needs to run only a low spec laptop from 5 years ago?) +1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● natural language queries for analysis ● Static approaches, minimal computing ● workbooks or templates for different processes (eg deploy a website, a database, a CMS etc) on a well used and secure platform or infrastructure ● graph databases? ● (graph databases?) which system are you thinking of? how would this manage access control? what type of querying? ● Focus on the new always marginalises well established but useful tools and approaches. We have a blindness for the past that holds us back. ● "(Focus on the new always marginalises well established but useful tools and approaches. We have a blindness for the past that holds us back.) 100% ● " ● (Focus on the new always marginalises well established but useful tools and approaches. We have a blindness for the past that holds us back.) Yeah but we do need to try new things as well ● vibe coding? ● cloud tech in general but alternatives to commercial cloud ● using severless or 'function as a service' FAAS ● vector search, semantic search ● Combining old things in new ways ● There are much more profound applications of AI. A recurring problem (touched on in previous Q) is the need to explore data first of all. There's amazing work going on in AI thematic analysis and visualisation of data of virtually any shape (HASS data isn't even at the difficult end of the scale for this). This is being actively explored by the Data Donation package in the ARDC umbrella package, the AIO. More broadly, and perhaps the lowest hanging fruit, is to do away with arcane UI and obscure syntax-based search operations and allow full text search queries. These systems are now fully developed and well understood in commercial practice. The research genre is considerably behind the times there, but then you'll see a LOT of this in products developed through the current round. Everything I do, certainly. (from survey)
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